

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC AND CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES OF METAL
 COMPLEXES OF 3-HYDROXY-1-*p*-SULPHONATOPHENYL-
 3-PHENYLTRIAZINE. PART IV. IRON COMPLEX

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Fe^{III} forms a bluish black, water-soluble complex with 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine. The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically by applying Job's continued variation method, slope ratio method and molar ratio method, has been found to be FeR₃ (R = reagent) in the pH range between 2.0 and 4.3. At higher pH values FeR²⁺ and FeR₂⁺ are indicated. Conductometrically all the three formulae are indicated. The dissociation constant of FeR₃ at 20° is 2.38×10^{-19} and the free energy of formation of the complex is -15.59 K cal./mole.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of iron (Gupta and Sogani, *this issue*, p. 97). From the absorption curves of iron complexes at different pH values and also from the effect of pH on absorbance (*loc. cit.*), iron complexes of different compositions at different H⁺-ion concentrations are indicated.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to establishing the formulae of iron-3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine complexes at different pH values, using spectrophotometric and conductometric methods. The empirical formula, in the pH range between 2.0 and 4.3, has been found to be FeR₃. The chelate structure may be represented as:

Job's continued variation method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) has been applied to study the formulae of iron complexes at higher pH values. At pH 5.5, the empirical formulae have been found to be FeR₁ and FeR₂ at 520 mμ and FeR₃ at 650 mμ. There is no indication of FeR₃ at this H⁺-ion concentration. Conductometrically all the above three formulae are indicated.

The dissociation constant and, hence, the stability constant, and the free energy of formation of iron complex, FeR₃, have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard ferric chloride solution, prepared as described (*loc. cit.*), was diluted to provide $M \times 10^{-3}$ for conductometric work and Job's method, and $M \times 10^{-4}$ and $M \times 10^{-5}$ for slope ratio method (Harve and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488). Reagent solution, buffer solutions, instruments, etc. were the same as described in Part I (*this Journal*, 1958, 35, 542).

Nature of the Complex Formed.—The absorption spectra of mixtures of equimolar solutions of ferric chloride and the reagent, in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, etc., at pH 2.5 and 5.5 were studied. The curves at pH 2.5 were different than those at pH 5.5 (Fig. 1, *loc. cit.*), thus indicating the formation of different complexes at different pH values (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437).

Composition of the Complex

The molar compositions of iron complexes were investigated by the following methods.

Job's Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from $M \times 10^{-3}$ solutions of the

metal and the reagent in which the ratios of iron to reagent varied from 1:11 to 11:1. In one set of experiments the pH was kept at about 2.5 and in the other set, at pH 5.5. Absorbance of the mixtures were measured at 520 and 650 m μ . At pH 2.5 the maxima at 3:9 ratio of iron to reagent at both the wavelengths indicated FeR_3 as the formula of the complex. Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained at pH 5.5. At 520 m μ the breaks in the curve at 4:8 and 6:6 ratios of iron to reagent indicate FeR_3 and FeR_1 as the formulae of the complexes. At 650 m μ , only FeR_3 is indicated. However, at higher pH there is no indication of FeR_3 .

FIG. 1

pH = 5.5-5.6. R = Reagent.

Slope Ratio Method.—There was some difficulty in applying this method for determining the formula of the iron complex. Though the colour formation was instantaneous, yet the solutions containing excess iron faded within 10 minutes. However, in case of excess of the reagent, the complex was fairly stable. The fading of the colour in the former case probably is due to the oxidising action of excess of ferric ions on the very low concentrations of the reagent. Because of this reason, the absorbance of different solutions was measured immediately after these were prepared. The concentration of the variable component was varied from 1×10^{-5} to $10 \times 10^{-5} M$ in the excess concentration of $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was kept at about 2.5. Fig. 2 records the measured optical density at 650 m μ , plotted against the concen-

FIG. 2
pH 2.5. 650 m μ .

tration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines afford iron to reagent ratio as 1 : 3.

Molar Ratio Method (Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111).—

FIG. 3

Varying amounts of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent solution were added to a series of solutions containing 5 c.c. of $10^{-3} M$ iron. pH was adjusted to about 2.5. There is a slight break in the curve 'a' (Fig. 3) at a ratio of 3 moles of the reagent to 1 mole of iron, suggesting the formula of the complex as FeR_3 . By repeating the above experiment in presence of 5 c.c. of $M-KCl$ a better break in the curve is obtained (curve 'b').

Conductivity Method.— $M \times 10^{-3}$ -ferric chloride (10 c.c., pH 2.5) solution was taken in a conductivity cell and its conductance was measured; $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ -reagent solution (pH 2.5, adjusted with HCl) was added from a burette. The observed conductance was corrected for volume. Fig. 4 shows the conductance values plotted against moles of the reagent added. The formation of three complexes: FeR^{3+} , FeR_2^+ and FeR_3 is indicated during the course of the reaction.

The reaction takes place in three steps. The equations may be written as:

Consider the first step (equation 1). During the course of reaction Fe^{3+} ions are replaced by less mobile FeR^{3+} complex ions and more mobile H^+ ions. The former decreases the conductance whereas the latter increases it. The latter effect more than compensates the decrease in conductance due to the former effect. The curve therefore shows a continuous increase in conductance. At the equivalence point there is a sudden disappearance of all Fe^{3+} and the conductance is due to only H^+ ions and FeR^{3+} ions; hence, there is a slight fall in the conductance. This indicates the formula of the complex,

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the complex may be written as :

where C is the concentration of the complex, assuming no dissociation, and α is the degree of dissociation. The dissociation constant, K , is given by the equation

$$K = \frac{C \times (3 \alpha C)^3}{C(1-\alpha)} = \frac{27 \alpha^4 C^3}{1-\alpha}$$

From curve 'a'. Fig. 3

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_n}{E_m} = \frac{0.45 - 0.24}{0.45} = 0.466$$

(where the terms have their usual significance). The concentration C of the complex is equal to the total concentration of iron, which is $10^{-4}M$.

By substituting these values in the above equation, the value of K at 20° comes to 2.38×10^{-13} . Hence, the stability constant K' is equal to 4.2×10^{11} .

The standard free energy of formation of the complex from ferric chloride and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine is calculated from the relation $\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$ and works out to $\cdot 15.59$ K cal./mole at 20° .

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